

Application of the digital twin framework for BIM-Based facility renovation management

MOHAMAD CHAABAN

Supervisors:

Žiga Turk

Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Abstract

This thesis explores the integration of building information modeling (BIM) with facility management and maintenance (FMM) using a functional Digital Twin workflow. It explains the development of BIM, FMM, and IoT along with their respective challenges and contributions to what a digital twin is. Moreover, a framework is developed that focuses on harnessing the main strengths of a digital twin through standardized naming inspired by ISO and COBie, defining a Common Data Environment (CDE) that leverages both the static information of a BIM model and the dynamic information of remote data services to build a functional facility management portfolio, and defining information requirements that enable the progression of a building information model into an Asset Information Model (AIM). Furthermore, a case study demonstrates the framework's application in a sample project. This research contributes to an organized BIM workflow that enables efficient facility management, sustainability, and data-driven decision-making.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/H3dA7n4SsCk>

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10034075